

Institution Based Tumor Registry, Benazir Bhutto Hospital: A Four Year Data Based Analysis.

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Abstract

Background: To retrieve all diagnosed cancer cases during the past four years (2014-2017) in Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi, and categorize them by organ sites affected/ topographically, to determine cancers with the highest prevalence in our part of the world.

Materials & Methods: A hospital registry-based retrospective study was undertaken in the Department of Pathology of Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi. All diagnosed cases of cancer for the past four years that had been histologically confirmed, were retrieved. The cancer cases thus obtained were then classified topographically, according to the International classification of diseases for oncology. The data obtained was then analyzed using SPSS v.23 into percentage frequencies and ranked with respect to gender, and presented using tables and figures.

Results: Urinary Bladder, Breast, Prostate, Skin, Kidney, Colorectum, Cervix, Esophagus, Uterus and Vulva were in descending order the 10 leading sites overall.

Carcinoma of the Urinary Bladder emerged as the leading cancer in males, comprising 30.7% of male cases, followed by Prostate (24.7%), Skin (16.3%), Colorectum (5.6%), Kidney (5.6%) and Stomach (2.4%).

The most common site of cancer in females was Breast (36.2%), followed in decreasing order by Cervix (8.6%), Kidney (7.6%), Urinary Bladder (7.1%), Skin (7.1%), and Esophagus (6.2%).

Conclusion: In conclusion, the cancer pattern revealed by this study provides valuable leads to cancer epidemiology in the region. The two most common cancer sites in males were urinary bladder (30.7%) and prostate (24.7%), whereas in females they were breast (36.2%) and cervix (8.6%).

Key Words: Tumor registry; Cancer pattern

Introduction:

Cancer is a serious health problem around the globe, with an estimated 14.1 million new cases and 8.2 million deaths annually. Out of these 14.1 million new cases, 8 million occurred in the developing countries in which about 80% of the world's population resides. By the year 2030, the global cancer burden is expected to grow to 21.7 million new cases and 13 million deaths annually, mainly due to the growth and aging of population.¹ However, it is said that the future cancer burden will be considerably larger than the current estimates because of adoption of lifestyles, such as smoking, physical inactivity, poor diet, fewer pregnancies, etc. that are believed to increase the risk for developing cancer.^{2,3}

In order to prevent and control cancers, there is an overwhelming need to establish and maintain cancer registries, which would then assist in formulating an effective health policy against the ever increasing cancer burden worldwide. The information obtained from these cancer registries can be used to look for trends over time, to find cancer patterns in certain geographical regions or populations, or to determine whether screening and other preventive measures are making any significant difference. Therefore, registries and surveillance information are key parts of cancer prevention and control efforts around the globe.⁴

The absence of any effective mechanism to collect and analyze credible data on prevalence of cancer in Pakistan is retarding us from taking appropriate measures for the timely diagnosis and treatment of this disease. Pakistan bears a significant cancer burden with rising trends of risk factors, thereby it is a country in dire need of cancer control.

The rationale behind this study was to retrieve all diagnosed cancer cases for the past four years (2014-2017) in Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi, and categorize them by organ sites affected/ topographically, to determine cancers with the highest prevalence in our part of the world. In the absence of a

population based cancer registry in Rawalpindi, this study along with previous reports may prove helpful in estimating the incidence of different cancers in the region.

Materials and Methods:

A 4 year hospital registry-based retrospective study from January 2014 to December 2017 was undertaken in the Department of Pathology of Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi, a tertiary care teaching hospital affiliated with Rawalpindi Medical University. All diagnosed cases of cancers for the past four years (2014-2017) that had been histologically confirmed, were retrieved. In situ or borderline cancers were excluded. A single entry per patient has been made in our data even when multiple samples may have been examined.

The cancer cases thus obtained were then classified on the basis of organ site affected, i.e. topographically, according to the International classification of diseases for oncology.⁵ Each tumor was assigned ICD-O code (International Classification of diseases for Oncology), published by International Agency for Research on cancer (IARC).⁵ The total number of cancer cases was calculated for each year. The data obtained was then analyzed using SPSS v.23 into percentage frequencies and ranked with respect to gender, and presented using tables and figures.

Results:

During the study period, a total of 461 cases of cancer were received of which 251 (54.4%) were males and 210 (45.6%) were females - sex ratio 1.2: 1 (Fig. I). There was an initial decrease followed by a progressive increase in the number of cancer cases per year during the study period i.e. 2014-2017. Figure II demonstrates the trend of cancer incidence over these four years of study.

Table I summarizes the most common malignancies according to rank that were seen in both males as well as in females. Urinary Bladder, Breast, Prostate, Skin, Kidney, Colorectum, Cervix, Esophagus, Uterus and Vulva were in descending order the 10 leading sites.

Cancer of the Urinary Bladder emerged as the leading cancer in males comprising 30.7% of male cases followed by Prostate (24.7%), Skin (16.3%), Colorectum (5.6%), Kidney (5.6%) and Stomach (2.4%) as presented in Table II.

On the other hand the most common site of cancer in females was Breast (36.2%), followed in decreasing order by Cervix (8.6%), Kidney (7.6%), Urinary

Bladder (7.1%), Skin (7.1%), and Esophagus (6.2%) as shown in Table III.

Fig. I: Percentage Distribution Among Males and Females

Fig II: Cancer Trend 2014-2017

TABLE I: Leading Cancer Sites Overall

RANK	SITE	ICD-O	No. OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
1.	Urinary Bladder	C67	92	20.0%
2.	Breast	C50	76	16.5%
3.	Prostate	C61	62	13.4%
4.	Skin	C44	56	12.1%
5.	Kidney	C64	30	6.5%
6.	Colorectal	C18-21	18	3.9%
7.	Cervix	C53	18	3.9%
8.	Esophagus	C15	18	3.9%
9.	Uterus	C54-55	10	2.2%
10.	Vulva	C51	10	2.2%
11.	Larynx	C32	8	1.7%
12.	Oral Cavity	C00-06	8	1.7%
13.	Stomach	C16	8	1.7%
14.	Ovary	C56	7	1.5%
15.	Lymph Node	C77	5	1.1%
16.	Pharynx	C10-14	4	0.9%

17.	Testis	C62	4	0.9%
18.	Vagina	C52	4	0.9%
19.	Other Sites	-	23	5.0%
Total			461	100%

TABLE II: Leading Cancer Sites In Males

RANK	SITE	ICD-O	No. OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
1.	Urinary Bladder	C67	77	30.7%
2.	Prostate	C61	62	24.7%
3.	Skin	C44	41	16.3%
4.	Colorectal	C18-21	14	5.6%
5.	Kidney	C64	14	5.6%
6.	Stomach	C16	6	2.4%
7.	Esophagus	C15	5	2.0%
8.	Larynx	C32	5	2.0%
9.	Oral Cavity	C0-06	4	1.6%
10.	Testis	C62	4	1.6%
11.	Lymph Node	C77	3	1.2%
12.	Pharynx	C10-14	3	1.2%
13.	Other Sites	-	13	5.2%
Total			251	100%

TABLE III: Leading Cancer Sites In Females

RANK	SITE	ICD-O	No. OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
1.	Breast	C50	76	36.2%
2.	Cervix	C53	18	8.6%
3.	Kidney	C64	16	7.6%
4.	Urinary Bladder	C67	15	7.1%
5.	Skin	C44	15	7.1%
6.	Esophagus	C15	13	6.2%
7.	Uterus	C54-55	10	4.8%
8.	Vulva	C51	10	4.8%
9.	Ovary	C56	7	3.3%
10.	Colorectal	C18-21	4	1.9%
11.	Oral Cavity	C0-06	4	1.9%
12.	Vagina	C52	4	1.9%
13.	Other Sites	-	18	8.6%
Total			210	100%

Discussion:

Epidemiological information on cancer including the incidence pattern is an essential tool for determining the priorities for cancer control in any population group. There are pronounced disparities in distribution of cancers in different regions of the world mainly due to differences in the prevailing environmental and sociocultural factors. These factors contributing to geographic differences include variations in the age structure of the population, the prevalence of risk factors (e.g., smoking, alcohol intake, dietary habits, etc.), the availability and use of diagnostic tests (e.g., for cancer screening) and the availability and quality of treatment.^{6,7}

We observed a significant increase in the incidence during the study period, which suggests an increase in the risk behavior in the population with lifestyle changes and deteriorating dietary habits. This increased incidence may also be attributed to improved diagnostic facilities over the years and increased accessibility to these facilities. Whatever may be cause of increased incidence, it supports the existing predictions of increasing cancer incidence and mortality in developing countries as the population continues to expand. It must be stated here that the number of cases retrieved in this study is actually an underestimation of the actual cancer burden in the region as our hospital is not the only tertiary care hospital in the region and also because the absence of an oncology unit in our hospital does not make it a natural choice of referral for cases having a high suspicion of malignancy. In addition, we may also be missing cases with advanced malignancies who may not be subjected to intense diagnostic procedures, older patients or females who may not be entering the health sector and the socio-economically deprived who may not have access to medical care.

Global cancer trends demonstrate a slight male predominance, also observed in our study with a male: female ratio of 1.2:1.⁶ The exact reason for this male preponderance is still unclear but it is believed that increased exposure to risk factors (e.g. smoking and alcohol consumption) in males, may be the underlying cause.

In our study, cancer of the urinary bladder came out to be the most common cancer overall, as well as in men comprising 30.7% of all male cases. In females it accounted for about 7.1% of all cases making it the fourth most common cancer in females. The wide sex ratio (male: female) exhibited in our study is in line with numerous international studies observing male predominance in cases of bladder cancer.^{6,8} There is

about 15 fold variation in incidence rates of bladder carcinoma internationally, partly due to differences in the reporting of low grade urinary bladder tumors (i.e. malignant but noninvasive).⁹ Smoking is the most established risk factor and is said to increase the risk of bladder carcinoma by two to six fold and cause about 31% of bladder cancer deaths among males and 14% among females worldwide.^{10,11} In this study urothelial carcinomas were far more prevalent than the squamous cell type which is associated with schistosomiasis and makes up about 3% of cases worldwide.¹²

The second most common cancer in men was that of prostate accounting for 24.7% of all male cases. Globally it is the second most frequently diagnosed cancer in men.⁶ Annual cancer registry report of Shaukat Khanum Cancer Hospital for the year 2016 stated colorectum and prostate as the leading cancer sites in men.¹³ A couple of local studies carried out in Rawalpindi and Hazara division regard prostate cancer as the first and third most common cancer among males respectively.^{14,15} The risk factors proven to be associated with prostate cancer are old age, family history and inherited genetic conditions. According to recent studies smoking is associated with prostate cancer death but not incidence.¹⁶

Breast cancer, the leading female cancer worldwide was the most common cancer among females making up 36.2% of all female cases. In almost all the local studies carried out in various regions of Pakistan, breast cancer was invariably the most common cancer in females.^{13-15, 17-20} Most of the cases of breast cancer in our study were of invasive ductal type. The high prevalence of breast cancer worldwide has been linked to reproductive factors, obesity, physical inactivity and changes in diet and lifestyle.²¹⁻²³ Early detection and treatment in developed countries has kept mortality from breast cancer under control. However in developing countries like ours, there is an urgent need to develop effective screening mechanisms for the early detection and subsequent treatment of breast cancer. Developing health programmes that promote breast self-examination, clinical breast examination, and FNAC along with mammographic screening may prove helpful.²⁴

Cervical cancer was the second most common cancer in females comprising 8.6% of total female cases. Globally it is the fourth most commonly diagnosed cancer in females with particularly high prevalence in developing countries where it is the second most common female malignancy.⁶ A study carried out in Punjab in the year 2014 showed cervical cancer as the

third most common cancer among females in the province.¹⁸ Annual cancer registry report of Shaukat Khanum Cancer Hospital for the year 2016 also reported cervical cancer as the fourth most common female malignancy.¹³ The large geographical variation in the incidence of cervical cancer around the globe reflects the differences in the screening efforts and vaccination status against HPV infection.²⁵

Cancers of the kidney ranked third among females (7.6%), and fifth in males (5.6%). Majority of these cases were renal cell carcinomas, followed by urothelial carcinomas. Kidney cancers are associated with smoking, obesity, hypertension and chronic kidney diseases. Attention given to the avoidance of these risk factors may be helpful in decreasing the incidence of renal cancers.

Skin cancers ranked third among males (16.3%), and fifth among females (7.1%). They were mainly squamous cell carcinomas and less frequently basal cell carcinomas. A previously carried out study in Rawalpindi, regarded skin as the second most common cancer site in both males as well as in females.¹⁴

Colorectal carcinoma was the fourth most common type of cancer in males making up 5.6% of total male cases. In various local studies, colorectal cancers have been consistently reported among the leading cancers in males.^{13,14,17} Screening can detect colorectal polyps before they become cancerous and thus removal of these precancerous polyps comprises a treatment modality that is less extensive and more successful.²⁶

A brief account of the most common cancers encountered in our study has been given above. It is important to state that the findings of this study should be taken cautiously and cannot be extrapolated for the entire region due to referral and other biases regarding hospital data. The variations observed in the results of various local studies also reinforce the fact that the results of these hospital registry based studies should be followed cautiously and also that the establishment of proper population based cancer registries has become absolutely necessary for obtaining credible information about cancer prevalence in our country.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the cancer pattern revealed by this study provides valuable leads to cancer epidemiology in the region. The two most common cancer sites in males were urinary bladder (30.7%) and prostate (24.7%), whereas in females they were breast (36.2%) and cervix (8.6%). In Pakistan, there is a great deficiency of population based cancer registries, in the

absence of which studies like these may prove useful for health planning, future research and effective cancer control.

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References:

1. Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, Ervik M, Dikshit R, Eser S, Mathers C, Rebelo M, Parkin DM, Forman D, Bray, F. GLOBOCAN 2012 v1.0, Cancer Incidence and Mortality Worldwide: IARC CancerBase No.11 [Internet]. Lyon, France: International Agency for Research on Cancer; 2013. Available from: <http://globocan.iarc.fr> [Accessed 22nd January 2018].
2. Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME). GBD Compare Data Visualization. Seattle, WA: IHME, University of Washington, 2016. Available from: <http://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-compare> [Accessed 25th January 2018].
3. Lozano R, Naghavi M, Foreman K, et al. Global and regional mortality from 235 causes of death for 20 age groups in 1990 and 2010: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010. *Lancet* 2013;380(9859):2095-2128.
4. International Agency for Research on Cancer. Global Initiative for Cancer Registry Development. Available from: <http://gicr.iarc.fr/>. [Accessed 30th January 2018].
5. International Classification of Diseases for Oncology, Third Edition, Topographical Codes, World Health Organization. Available from: <http://codes.iarc.fr/topography> [Accessed 11th January 2018].
6. American Cancer Society. Global Cancer Facts & Figures 3rd Edition. Atlanta: American Cancer Society; 2015. Available from: <https://www.cancer.org/content/dam/cancer-org/research/cancer-facts-and-statistics/global-cancer-facts-and-figures/global-cancer-facts-and-figures-3rd-edition.pdf> [Accessed 30th January 2018].
7. Stewart B. W. and Kleihues P. (Eds): World Cancer Report. IARC Press. Lyon 2003. Available from: <http://www.iarc.fr/en/publications/pdfs-online/wcr/2003/WorldCancerReport.pdf> [Accessed 3rd February 2018].
8. Mohammed, AZ & T Edino, S & Ochicha, Ochicha & Kuliya-Gwarzo, Aisha & Samaila, AA.. Cancer in Nigeria: A 10-Year Analysis of the Kano Cancer Registry. *Nigerian Journal of Medicine* 2008;17(3):280-284.
9. Chavan S, Bray F, Lortet-Tieulent J, Goodman M, Jemal A. International variations in bladder cancer incidence and mortality. *Eur Urol* 2014;66(1):59-73.
10. Parkin DM. The global burden of urinary bladder cancer. *Scand J Urol Nephrol Suppl* 2008(218):12-20.
11. Freedman ND, Silverman DT, Hollenbeck AR, Schatzkin A, Abnet CC. Association Between Smoking and Risk of Bladder Cancer Among Men and Women. *JAMA* 2011;306(7):737-745.
12. Parkin DM. The global health burden of infection-associated cancers in the year 2002. *Int J Cancer* 2006;118(12):3030-3044.
13. Mahmood S. Annual cancer registry report-2016. Shaukat khanum.org; 2016; 1-21. Available from: <http://shaukatkhanum.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/acrr-2016.pdf> [Accessed 4th February 2018].
14. Jamal S, Moghal S, Mamoon N, Mushtaq S, Luqman M, Anwar M. The pattern of malignant tumours: tumour registry data analysis, AFIP, Rawalpindi, Pakistan (1992-2001). *J Pak Med Assoc* 2006;56(8):359-62.
15. Ahmad S, Qureshi N. First cancer statistics report from hazara division. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad* 2013;25:1-2.
16. Islami F, Moreira DM, Boffetta P, Freedland SJ. A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of Tobacco Use and Prostate Cancer Mortality and Incidence in Prospective Cohort Studies. *Eur Urol* 2014;66(6):1054-64.
17. Adnan N, Rasheed G, Nadeem S, et al. Hospital-Based Cancer Registry. *Journal of Rawalpindi Medical College (JRMC)* 2017;21(4): 349-353.
18. Masood K, Masood A, Zafar J, Shahid A, Kamran M. Trends and Analysis of Cancer Incidence for Common Male and Female Cancers in the Population of Punjab Province of Pakistan during 1984 to 2014. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention* 2015;16(13):5297-5304.
19. Hanif M, Zaidi P, Kamal S, Hameed A. Institution-based cancer incidence in a local population in Pakistan: nine year data analysis. *Asian Pac J Cancer PreV* 2009;10(2):227-30.
20. Z. Aziz, S. Sana, S. Saeed, M. Akram. Institution Based Tumor Registry from Punjab: Five Year Data Based Analysis. *JPMA (Journal Of Pakistan Medical Association)* 2003;53(8).
21. Chlebowski RT. Nutrition and physical activity influence on breast cancer incidence and outcome. *Breast* 2013;22S2:S30-S37.
22. Catsburg C, Miller AB, Rohan TE. Active cigarette smoking and risk of breast cancer. *Int J Cancer* 2015;136(9):2204-9.
23. Dossus L, Boutron-Ruault MC, Kaaks R, et al. Active and passive cigarette smoking and breast cancer risk: results from the EPIC cohort. *Int J Cancer* 2014;134: 1871-1888.
24. Okonkwo QL, Draisma G, der Kinderen A, Brown ML, de Koning H. Breast cancer screening policies in developing countries: a cost-effectiveness analysis for India. *J Natl Cancer Inst* 2008;100:1290-1300.
25. Vaccarella S, Lortet-Tieulent J, Plummer M, Franceschi S, Bray F. Worldwide trends in cervical cancer incidence: Impact of screening against changes in disease risk factors. *Eur J Cancer* 2013 Oct;49(15):3262-73
26. H. Gilbert Welch, Douglas J. Robertson. Colorectal Cancer on the Decline — Why Screening Can't Explain It All. *N Engl J Med* 2016; 374:1605-1607.